

How does science influence policy? Insight into citation relationships between AI policies and research articles

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Abstract: The importance of science-based policy support has been widely recognized, but how science influences policy remains insufficiently explored. This study aims to examine how policies cite research articles and trace the complex interplay between research and policymaking. Based on over 1.6 million citation links between articles and policies related to artificial intelligence (AI), diverse types of simple or intricate pathways of policies citing articles are identified. Whereas articles from EU countries primarily serve policymaking of inter-governmental organizations (IGOs) and EU, articles from USA significantly support both domestic and foreign policymaking. Notably, IGOs' policies are crucial intermediaries for articles to indirectly influence policymaking. Another finding is that natural science has increasingly participated in the formulation of AI-related policies. Besides providing these new observations, this contribution develops new concepts and methods for both the direct and indirect policy impact of research by taking into account how different policy formulations influence each other.

1. Introduction

Since the 20th century, an increasingly intricate interplay has evolved among science, technology and society. The *Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment* (2022), signed by more than 350 organizations from over 40 countries, emphasizes the recognition of broader impacts of research outcomes. One significant aspect of broader impacts lies in the role scientific research plays in informing and shaping policymaking.

Generally, there are four distinct relationships between science and policy: knowledge shapes policy, politics shapes knowledge, co-production, and autonomous spheres (Boswell & Smith, 2017). This study delves into the first relationship – the role of scientific knowledge and ideas in policy formulation and adjustment. The emphasis on the impact of science on policy is associated with the emergence of evidence-based medicine in 1990s (Sur & Dahm, 2011). Scientific research is considered crucial in evidence-based decision-making (Pawson, 2002). However, the gap between science and policy poses a significant dilemma. Policymakers may overlook vital scientific insights, and flawed scientific advice could adversely affect decision-making (Weiss, 1979). Klautzer et al. (2011) have found that scientific research is often perceived as changing policy in an incremental way. Understanding how science influences policy contributes to tackling this dilemma (Almeida & Báscolo, 2006).

Previous studies exploring the integration of scientific research in policymaking (Cheng, Tang, Zhou & Wang, 2021; Edler, Karaulova & Barker, 2022; Hu, Huang & Bu, 2024; Ren & Yang, 2023; Xu & Zong, 2023; Yin, Gao, Jones & Wang, 2021) primarily focus on the “presence or absence” and “abundance or scarcity” of policy impact. How scientific research incrementally affects policymaking remains inadequately elucidated. Figure 1 below illustrates the possible complexity of the influences: While Article 1 and Article 2 both receive two policy citations, the latter exerts a more enduring, extensive, and intricate impact compared to the former. Focusing on various patterns of policies citing articles, this study addresses following questions: (1) How long are the temporal gaps between the release of policies and the publication of referenced research articles? (2) What patterns of pathways can be observed? (3) What kind of flows occur between authors of articles and policy issuing institutions along these pathways? (4) What are the thematic features of policies and their referenced articles? This study aims to uncover the multidimensional and complex nature of policy citations compared to academic citations, offering novel insights for policy impact assessment.

Figure 1: Different patterns of policies citing articles.

2. Data and methods

2.1 Key concepts

Our analysis is conducted based on heterogeneous citation networks composed of policy and article nodes. Two-generation references of focal policies (FPs) are traced. On one hand, referenced articles (RAs) and referenced policies (RPs) cited by FPs are considered. On the other hand, RPs' referenced articles (RPAs) and RPs' referenced policies (RPPs), which are indirectly connected to FPs, are considered.

Figure 2: Illustration on key concepts

2.2 Research data

This study focuses on policies within the realm of artificial intelligence (AI), which is characterized by a distinct sci-tech-driven nature. Over recent years, AI has exerted profound influences on various facets of our society, and captured the attention of policymakers. Simultaneously, the advancement of AI invariably gives rise to ethical and legal quandaries necessitating policy intervention, consequently spawning a multitude of pertinent policies. Therefore, it presents an apt realm for examining the interaction between science and policy. At the practical level, Overton, the largest collection of policy documents (Szomszor & Adie, 2022), is selected as our main data source. This platform employs machine learning techniques to extract topics from the full text of each policy document indexed and map them to a taxonomy¹, presented as a filter on the platform website, facilitating access to AI-related policies and their references.

As of 2023, Overton has indexed 37,306 policy documents labelled with the topic of AI², among which 17,105 policy documents have cited scholarly articles or policies. These policies can be traced back to as early as 1970, and they were promulgated by various types of institutions including *government*, *think tank*, *inter-governmental organization (IGO)* and *others*. We establish two additional constraints to determine our samples. Firstly, policy issuing institutions are confined to *government* and *IGO*. Policies issued by these institutions typically carry greater authority and represent the official will of a nation or a collective of nations, thereby possessing significant political impact. Other types of institutions such as think tanks are excluded

¹ <https://help.overton.io/article/about-topics-entities-and-subject-areas/>

² According to statistics on February 28, 2024.

primarily due to their supportive roles in decision-making, policies released by which are more advisory instead of interventionist. Secondly, we limit the policy release year to 2016 and onwards. The year 2016 is widely regarded as the dawn of AI. In this year, AlphaGo won the world's top human Go player; the US's Federal Government published the first *National AI R&D Strategic Plan*, recognizing AI's tremendous promise and need for continued advancement. In our dataset, approximately 95% of the policies were issued from 2016 onwards, marking the onset of a rapid growth phase since that year. 9,963 policies released by governmental institutions within years 2016~2023 are selected as our research samples.

The 9,963 focal policies (FPs) have 87,677 referenced articles (RAs) and 39,183 referenced policies (RPs). By retrieving the RPs' references, 402,279 referenced articles of RPs (RPAs) are received. Given the broad definition of *scholarly articles* in Overton, which involves non-research-oriented papers, this study employs the definition of *journal-article* provided by OpenAlex, to constrain the types of RAs and RPAs within a more precise scope. Using digital object identifiers (DOIs) to link data of articles indexed in OpenAlex, 60,991 RAs and 291,589 RPAs with the type of *journal-article* can be obtained, covering 7,833 (79%) FPs. These articles and policies are our final focus, including 101,514 FP-RA pairs and 1,531,209 FP-RP-RPA pairs, based on which the impact of scientific research on policymaking is investigated.

2.3 Research methods

Employing bibliometric and network analysis methods, large-scale data analysis and fine-grained case analysis are combined to investigate how policies cite articles. The former enables us to grasp general patterns of the sample population, while the latter facilitates a more intuitive understanding of complex features.

3. Results

3.1 Time lag of citing articles in policy documents

The impact of scientific research on policymaking exhibits distinct temporal characteristics. While some articles quickly attract attention from policies upon publication, others may require a longer time window to accumulate policy citations. The gestation period required is associated with factors such as the inherent characteristics of articles and the actual needs of policies.

Figure 3 illustrates the time delay from the year cited articles (RAs) published to the year citing policies (FPs) released. Our first observation is that over 60% of citations from policies are generated within 5 years since the publication of articles, and nearly 80% of those are within 10 years. 2~4 years after publication seem to be the golden window for generating policy impact. We also observed that over time, there has been a certain degree of reduction in the time interval of policies citing articles. Nevertheless, "sleeping beauty" articles (Van Raan, 2004) in the sense of policy impact do exist. For example, Cohen and Levinthal's research (1990) on the absorptive capacity of companies and their innovative activities was firstly cited by an AI-related policy in 2016 and has received citations from 11 unique policies in our dataset.

Figure 3: Time interval of policies citing articles.

Note: (1) Different years when FP-RA links were established are distinguished by colours. (2) Two sets of threshold lines are marked, respectively representing time intervals corresponding to 50% and 80% of the links being below the abscissa values of the vertical lines.

3.2 Pathway of policies citing articles

Figure 4 illustrates four distinct types of pathways of policies citing articles. The first distinction to be made is the direct or indirect impact of articles on policies. The former manifests in articles (RAs) cited by focal policies (FPs), while the latter reflects the potential capacity of articles (RPAs) to influence policymaking through the dissemination of other policies (RPs). The second distinction to be made is the existence of reinforcement effect (Lü, Chen & Zhou, 2011). Articles can support the formulation of focal policies together with its citing articles, or with other policies it has influenced. If an article node is connected to a policy node through multiple links, it can be considered to have a stronger impact on the policy compared to when there is only one link available.

Figure 4: Four types of pathways of policies citing articles.

Note: When a given node is connected to another given node through multiple intermediary nodes, the link between two given nodes is relatively weak. Thus, the illustration presented here solely contemplates the scenario where the subsidiary pathway comprises a single node. In such instances, the collaborative support between articles and their citing articles/policies towards focal policies is notably pronounced.

Both direct and indirect policy impact have been observed in our dataset. Among 7,833 policies, 1,172 policies (15%) only have first-generation referenced articles; 2,145 policies (27%) only have second-generation referenced articles, indirectly influenced by scientific research; 4,516 policies (58%) have both first- and second-generation referenced articles. The joint supportive role of articles and their citing policies/articles in focal policies is also remarkable. Among 101,514 FP-RA pairs, 55% and 45% of them respectively belong to Type A1 and Type A2. Among 1,531,209 FP-RP-RPA pairs, 48% and 52% of them respectively belong to Type B1 and Type B2.

3.3 Geographical flows between authors of articles and policy issuing institutions

Which country's (region's) institutions issue policies that cite articles signed by authors from which country (region)? Do any institutions act as intermediaries in this process? Figure 5 illustrates the influences across countries and regions of authors³ and policy issuing institutions in FP-RA pairs and FP-RP-RPA pairs. In subplot (a), a clear contrast is observed between USA and EU countries such as Germany, Netherlands and Italy. Articles from the former significantly support both domestic and foreign policy formulation, whereas articles from the latter primarily serve IGO's and EU's policymaking, with relatively weak support for domestic and other countries' policies. In subplot (b), the prominence of IGOs as intermediate organizations and the visibility of several FP countries such as Uganda, Chile and Slovenia, are noteworthy. Some FP countries exhibit limited direct incorporation of scientific research in their policy formulation, highly dependent on globally influential institutions such as IGOs. It can be inferred that endorsing policymaking by globally influential bodies represents a potential avenue for amplifying the policy impact of scientific research. It is worth mentioning that China, with prominent international research outputs (especially in computer science), does not exhibit

³ Considering that the first author typically represents the primary contributor throughout the research process (Peidu, 2019), the affiliated country of the first author can be regarded as the principal intellectual source of the scientific research. Therefore, in this study, only the country of the first author's affiliating institution is considered.

a comparable proportion of articles cited by policies in relevant realms. This, to some extent, reflects that despite notable international publications, the global impact of China’s research on AI-related policies remains relatively limited.

Figure 5: Country (region) flows in the process of policies citing articles.

Note: In consideration of the abundant volume of policies issued by inter-governmental organizations (IGOs) and their large scale of references, graphical representation is conducted by taking the square root of the weights between countries (regions) for the purpose of clearly delineating each node.

Zooming into pathways with more than one policy, we further take the institution types into consideration. Table 1 delineates different transmission routes of policy issuing institutions, each route possessing its own significance. For example, an article was cited by policy P1 from a regional non-governmental institution⁴. P1 was then cited by policy P2 from a regional governmental body. Subsequently, P2 was cited by policy P3 from an international organization. It reflects a “bottom-up” route of influence. Conversely, if aforementioned policies P1, P2 and P3 were respectively released by an international organization, a regional governmental body, and a regional non-governmental institution, it reflects a “top-down” route of influence. In our dataset, transmission routes of 1,142,933 RPA-RP-FP pairs with full institutional information can be identified. The numbers of pairs corresponding to Route 1-4 are respectively 779,571 (68.21%), 6,305 (0.55%), 269,266 (23.56%) and 87,791 (7.68%). In comparison, policies indirectly influenced by articles and those serving as intermediaries are more often issued by

⁴ As mentioned in Section 2, for focal policies, we only consider governmental institutions with types of *government* and *IGO* to restrict the properties of policy documents. But for referenced policies, the crucial intermediary role of other-type institutions such as think tanks is observed, so non-governmental institutions are also considered.

institutions of the same type. There seem to be certain challenges for policy impact to cross geographical boundaries as well.

Table 1. Classification of transmission routes among policy issuing institutions.

Criteria 1: country/region (CR)	Criteria 2: institution type	Cases		Classification
		Cited entity	Citing entity	
Within a country/region	Between institutions with the same type	Non-governmental institution from CR A	Non-governmental institution from CR A	Route 1 779,571 68.21%
		Governmental institution from CR A	Governmental institution from CR A	
	Between institutions with various types	Non-governmental institution from CR A	Governmental institution from CR A	Route 2 6,305 0.55%
		Governmental institution from CR A	Non-governmental institution from CR A	
Across countries/regions	Between institutions with the same type	Governmental institution from CR A	Governmental institution from CR B	Route 3 269,266 23.56%
		Non-governmental institution from CR A	Non-governmental institution from CR B	
	Between institutions with various types	Governmental institution from CR A	Non-governmental institution from CR B	Route 4 87,791 7.68%
		Non-governmental institution from CR A	Governmental institution from CR B	

3.4 Thematic features of policies and referenced articles

Based on the 19 root-level concepts of the six-layer taxonomy developed by OpenAlex⁵, Figure 6 compares the annual trends of distribution of research fields between first- and second-generation referenced articles of AI-related policies. It can be observed that fields such as *Economics* and *Psychology* held prominent shares in earlier periods. It is not until the past two decades that research in *Computer science* is progressively cited by focal policies. In comparison, the dominance of social sciences has persisted for a longer duration in second-generation referenced articles. The above observations indicate that while the development of AI fundamentally depends on technological innovation, early-time policies primarily focus on its legal implications and its impacts on socio-economic, cultural, and psychological aspects. However, in recent years, natural science research has increasingly influenced the policy-making process.

⁵ See details about the taxonomy provided by OpenAlex in: <https://docs.openalex.org/api-entities/concepts>.

Figure 6: Annual trends of distribution of research fields of referenced articles.

Note: Earlier years with relatively few articles are not showcased in the figures.

Large-scale data analysis above underscores the overall trends in the thematic evolution of scientific research. However, for a better understanding of the intrinsic logic behind policy citing articles, delving deeper into the text for a more nuanced examination is necessary. For example, the research objective of an article informs us whether it is conducted under the motivation of supporting policy formulation; the context of a policy document where an article is cited informs us how it is specifically utilized by the policy (Newson, Rychetnik, King, Milat & Bauman, 2018). Such perspectives will be discussed in our subsequent case study.

3.5 In-depth analyses based on case study

In October 2022, the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) released *Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights*, aimed at guiding the design, use and deployment of automated systems to protect the American public in the AI era. This document was released one year after OSTP announced to develop a “bill of rights for an AI-powered world”. Its release follows a year of public engagement to inform this initiative.

As of the data retrieval date (February 6, 2024), policy F has been cited by 26 policies (C-P), which are further cited by 89 policies (C-P-P). 7 research articles (R-A) and 5 policies (R-P) have been cited by policy F, while 10 research articles (R-P-A) and 4 policies (R-P-P) have been cited by R-P-type policies. Subsequent analyses are conducted based on the citation network composed of the above seven groups of nodes, as shown in Figure 7.

From the temporal perspective, time delays for R-A-type articles to influence policy F are generally shorter than that for R-P-A-type articles, which can be explained by the longer period required for the accumulation of citations across multiple generations. It is noteworthy that article R-A1 was published in 1979 and received citation from policy F after 43 years. This article examines the roles of professional engineers within the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration in USA and how their professional backgrounds influence policymaking within the agency. From the context of F citing R-A1 (see Appendix 1), the article supports for the argument on how principles proposed by the policy can be implemented. In fact, this is the only instance of a policy citation for article R-A1 (according to Overton statistics), suggesting that the occurrence of policy impact is somewhat unpredictable, yet it also demonstrates that the potential policy impact of articles can occur within a long-term perspective.

Figure 7: Article-policy citation network.

From the structural perspective, the policy F is influenced by research articles in either simplistic or intricate ways (see Table 2). Articles R-A1, R-A4, R-A7 are cited by policy F, with a single link between articles and the policy. Articles R-P1-A1, R-P1-A2, R-P1-A3, R-P1-A4, R-P1-A5, R-P1-A6, R-P2-A3, R-P2-A4 are cited by policies R-P1 or R-P2 and indirectly influence policy F, with a single link between articles and F. Above two pathways respectively constitute the most basic structures for the first- and second-generation referenced articles to influence policy F. More complex cases include the following: articles R-A2, R-A5 are cited by policy F, with multiple links between articles and the policy; articles R-P2-A1, R-P2-A2 are cited by the referenced policies of policy F, with multiple links between articles and F. These articles are cited together with their citing articles or policies to jointly support the formulation of the focal policy. Additionally, article R-A3, R-A6 are cited by policy F with multiple and single link respectively, and also by the citing policies of F. These articles further influence the formulation of policies supported by the focal policy.

Table 2. Different types of pathways in the case.

Type	Description	Articles cited by policy F
A1	Direct impact with single link	R-A1, R-A4, R-A7
		R-A6 (further cited by the citing policies of policy F)
A2	Direct impact with multiple links	R-A2, R-A5
		R-A3 (further cited by the citing policies of policy F)
B1	Indirect impact with single link	R-P1-A1, R-P1-A2, R-P1-A3, R-P1-A4, R-P1-A5, R-P1-A6, R-P2-A3, R-P2-A4
B2	Indirect impact with multiple links	R-P2-A1, R-P2-A2

Note: The numerical designations of the types in this table are aligned with those in Figure 4.

From the perspective of entities, the process of policy F citing articles only involves the transmission from non-governmental to governmental institutions in USA. However, considering nodes with C-P and C-P-P types leads to more intriguing findings. For example, the chain R-P2-A1>>R-P2-A2>>R-P2-A3&R-P2-A4>>R-P2>>F>>C-P2>>C-P8>>C-P8-P1 illustrates the transmission from a conference paper to journal articles, successively influencing policies released by USA's think tank, USA's government, UK's government, IGO and the EU. This process reflects the gradual emergence and expansion of policy impact. Equally noteworthy, article R-A6 not only influences citing policies of policy F but also supports policies issued by different countries and types of institutions, such as C-P1 (USA's think tank) and C-P2-P1 (UK's government). This article, a conference paper primarily authored by researchers from Google Inc, can be regarded as generating diverse policy impact.

To study the contents, we manually examined the abstract of each article in the network. We found that first-generation referenced articles mostly elucidate their recommendations for policymakers in the abstracts and align with the topic of policy F, whereas second-generation referenced articles seldom discuss their policy implications and exhibit certain differences from the topic of policy F. We also noticed that the content of articles in pathways with multiple links demonstrate a closer alignment with the focal policy. For example, for article R-A2 and its multi-generation citations co-cited by policy F, a close association in terms of topics and research aims can be observed among them.

4. Conclusion and discussion

This study investigates how scientific research influences policymaking, taking the field of artificial intelligence as an example. Through large-scale data analysis and case studies, we elucidate the complex and diverse pathways of policies citing research articles. Statistics indicate that policy citations primarily occur within five years following the publication of research articles, with inter-governmental organizations playing a crucial role in the dissemination of policy impacts. Researchers may seize the time window and intermediates to raise the policy impact of scientific research. Furthermore, we have observed an increasing influence of natural science and computer science in policymaking, which contributes to the development of evidence-based decision-making (Keyfitz, 1995). Additionally, we have identified regional variations in the policy impact of scientific research. Our findings contribute to an enhanced understanding of the formation pathways of policy impact distinctive from citation impact, thus providing support for research evaluation.

It is necessary to acknowledge limitations of this study. Firstly, policies indexed in Overton are dominated by North America and Europe, potentially overlooking policies from countries such as China. Our findings necessitate further validation within a more comprehensive dataset. Secondly, this study focuses solely on AI-related policies. Yet differences may exist among disciplines. Caution should be exercised when generalizing our conclusions although our methods may prove useful in general. Our future work will expand our analysis to encompass a wider range of disciplines, longer time spans, and more geographical regions.

Open science practices

The data utilized in this study are publicly accessible. Specifically, the policy data, along with their respective references and citations, were obtained from the Overton platform, access to which necessitates the submission of an application. The article data were sourced from OpenAlex, a platform widely employed in quantitative science studies owing to its expansive data coverage and open-access features. Nonetheless, it is pertinent to acknowledge that the Overton platform restricts batch retrieval of data, thereby imposing a certain degree of challenge on data acquisition for the researchers. Nevertheless, open science practices have significantly aided the advancement of this study.

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Competing interests

Authors have no competing interests.

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References

Almeida, C. & Báscolo, E. (2006). Use of research results in policy decision-making, formulation, and implementation: a review of the literature. *Cadernos de Saúde Pública*, 22(suppl), S7-S19.

Boswell, C. & Smith, K. (2017). Rethinking policy ‘impact’: four models of research-policy relations. *Palgrave Communications*, 3(1), 1-10.

Cheng, X., Tang, L., Zhou, M. & Wang, G. (2021). Coevolution of COVID-19 research and China’s policies. *Health research policy and systems*, 19, 1-16.

CoARA. (2022). Agreement on Reforming Research Rssessment. https://coara.eu/app/uploads/2022/09/2022_07_19_rra_agreement_final.pdf

Cohen, W. M. & Levinthal, D. A. (1990). Absorptive capacity: A new perspective on learning and innovation. *Administrative science quarterly*, 35(1), 128-152.

Edler, J., Karaulova, M. & Barker, K. (2022). Understanding conceptual impact of scientific knowledge on policy: The role of policymaking conditions. *Minerva*, 60(2), 209-233.

Hu, L., Huang, W. B. & Bu, Y. (2024). Interdisciplinary research attracts greater attention from policy documents: evidence from COVID-19. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 11(1), 1-10.

Keyfitz, N. (1995). Inter-disciplinary contradictions and the influence of science on policy. *Policy Sciences*, 28(1), 21-38.

Klautzer, L., Hanney, S., Nason, E., Rubin, J., Grant, J. & Wooding, S. (2011). Assessing policy and practice impacts of social science research: the application of the Payback Framework to assess the Future of Work programme. *Research Evaluation*, 20(3), 201-209.

Lü, L., Chen, D. B. & Zhou, T. (2011). The small world yields the most effective information spreading. *New Journal of Physics*, 13(12), 123005.

Newson, R., Rychetnik, L., King, L., Milat, A. & Bauman, A. (2018). Does citation matter? Research citation in policy documents as an indicator of research impact—an Australian obesity policy case-study. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 16, 1-12.

Pawson, R. (2002). Evidence-based policy: The promise of ‘realist synthesis’. *Evaluation*, 8(3), 340-358.

Peidu, C. (2019). Can authors’ position in the ascription be a measure of dominance?. *Scientometrics*, 121, 1527-1547.

Ren, C. & Yang, M. (2023). Study on the Characteristics of Cross - Domain Knowledge Diffusion from Science to Policy: Evidence from Overton Data. *Proceedings of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 60(1), 368-378.

Sur, R. L. & Dahm, P. (2011). History of evidence-based medicine. *Indian Journal of Urology*, 27(4), 487-489.

Szomszor, M. & Adie, E. (2022). Overton: A bibliometric database of policy document citations. *Quantitative Science Studies*, 3(3), 624-650.

Van Raan, A. F. (2004). Sleeping beauties in science. *Scientometrics*, 59(3), 467-472.

Weiss, C. (1979). The Many Meanings of Research Utilization. *Public Administration Review*, 39(5), 426-431.

Xu, C. & Zong, Q. (2023). The effects of international research collaboration on the policy impact of research: A causal inference drawing on the journal Lancet. *Journal of Information Science*, 01655515231174381.

Yin, Y., Gao, J., Jones, B. F. & Wang, D. (2021). Coevolution of policy and science during the pandemic. *Science*, 371(6525), 128-130.

Appendix

Appendix 1 Citation context

Link of policy F: <https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Blueprint-for-an-AI-Bill-of-Rights.pdf>

Link of article R-A1: <https://doi.org/10.2307/976213>

Figure A1: Context of policy F citing article R-A1

EXECUTIVE ORDER 13960 ON PROMOTING THE USE OF TRUSTWORTHY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FEDERAL GOVERNMENT REQUIRES THAT CERTAIN FEDERAL AGENCIES ADHERE TO NINE PRINCIPLES WHEN DESIGNING, DEVELOPING, ACQUIRING, OR USING AI FOR PURPOSES OTHER THAN NATIONAL SECURITY OR DEFENSE. These principles—while taking into account the sensitive law enforcement and other contexts in which the federal government may use AI, as opposed to private sector use of AI—require that AI is: (a) lawful and respectful of our Nation’s values; (b) purposeful and performance-driven; (c) accurate, reliable, and effective; (d) safe, secure, and resilient; (e) understandable; (f) responsible and traceable; (g) regularly monitored; (h) transparent; and, (i) accountable. The Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights is consistent with the Executive Order. Affected agencies across the federal government have released AI use case inventories¹³ and are implementing plans to bring those AI systems into compliance with the Executive Order or retire them.

THE LAW AND POLICY LANDSCAPE FOR MOTOR VEHICLES SHOWS THAT STRONG SAFETY REGULATIONS—AND MEASURES TO ADDRESS HARMS WHEN THEY OCCUR—CAN ENHANCE INNOVATION IN THE CONTEXT OF COMPLEX TECHNOLOGIES. Cars, like automated digital systems, comprise a complex collection of components. The National Highway Traffic Safety Administration,¹⁴ through its rigorous standards and independent evaluation helps make sure vehicles on our roads are safe without limiting manufacturers’ ability to innovate.¹⁵ At the same time, rules of the road are implemented locally to impose contextually appropriate requirements on drivers, such as slowing down near schools or playgrounds.¹⁶

FROM LARGE COMPANIES TO START-UPS, INDUSTRY IS PROVIDING INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS THAT ALLOW ORGANIZATIONS TO MITIGATE RISKS TO THE SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF AI SYSTEMS, BOTH BEFORE DEPLOYMENT AND THROUGH MONITORING OVER TIME.¹⁷ These innovative solutions include risk assessments, auditing mechanisms, assessment of organizational procedures, dashboards to allow for ongoing monitoring, documentation procedures specific to model assessments, and many other strategies that aim to mitigate risks posed by the use of AI to companies’ reputation, legal responsibilities, and other product safety and effectiveness concerns.